

Annex A.3 – Antimicrobial resistance in *Salmonella* spp.

Annex to:

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Annex A.3.1 - High-level resistance to ciprofloxacin among certain *Salmonella* serovars

High-level resistance to ciprofloxacin in *S. Kentucky*

Figure 1: Resistance levels among MDR *Salmonella* Kentucky isolates exhibiting high-level ciprofloxacin resistance from food-producing animals, reported by MSs in 2022-2023

High-level resistance to ciprofloxacin among other *Salmonella* serovars

Figure 2: Number of *Salmonella* isolates displaying high-level ciprofloxacin resistance by serovar, reported from the different food-producing animal populations by MSs in 2022-2023

Annex A.3.2 Temporal trends in *Salmonella* serovars from poultry populations

a)

b)

c)

Figure 3: Temporal trends in resistance to selected antimicrobials in *Salmonella* Infantis from a) boilers, b) laying hens, and c) turkeys, all reporting countries, 2014-2022

a)

b)

Figure 4: Temporal trends in resistance to selected antimicrobials in *Salmonella* Enteritidis from a) boilers and b) laying hens, all reporting countries, 2014-2022

Annex A.3.3 – Occurrence of antimicrobial resistance at the *Salmonella* serovar level

Complete susceptibility and multidrug resistance

The patterns of resistance associated with different serovars influenced the overall resistance levels in *Salmonella* isolates. In the main part of the report, the proportion of CS and MDR isolates among *S. Typhimurium*, monophasic *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Derby*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Kentucky* from food-producing animals and humans are detailed. However, other serovars frequently recovered from each food-producing animal population also influence overall resistance levels in *Salmonella*. **Figure 5** and **Figure 6** show the proportions of isolates completely susceptible, resistant to 1 or 2 antimicrobial classes and MDR in *Salmonella* spp. and the most frequently recovered serovars from fattening pigs and cattle under 1 year of age in 2023, and broiler, laying hen and turkey flocks in 2022, respectively. Of note, are the very high MDR levels observed in **S. Rissen** from pigs (50.7%, N = 142) and **S. Newport** from broilers (66.7%, N = 36), and extremely high MDR levels in **S. Bredeney** from turkeys (88.2%, N = 76).

(a)

(b)

N: Total number of isolates recovered; *monophasic *S. Typhimurium* includes antigenic formulas.

The MDR analysis of animal isolates included the following antimicrobials: ampicillin, cefotaxime/ceftazidime, chloramphenicol, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, gentamicin/amikacin, meropenem, sulfamethoxazole, tetracycline/ tigecycline and trimethoprim.

Figure 5: Proportions of isolates completely susceptible (green), resistant to 1 or 2 antimicrobial classes (gold), and MDR (red) in *Salmonella* spp. and certain serovars recovered from (a) fattening pigs, and (b) cattle under 1 year of age (calves), for all reporting countries, 2023

a)

(b)

(c)

N: Total number of isolates recovered; *monophasic *S. Typhimurium* includes antigenic formulas.

The MDR analysis of animal isolates included the following antimicrobials: ampicillin, cefotaxime/ceftazidime, chloramphenicol, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, gentamicin/amikacin, meropenem, sulfamethoxazole, tetracycline/ tigecycline and trimethoprim.

Figure 6: Proportions of isolates completely susceptible (green), resistant to 1 or 2 antimicrobial classes (gold), and MDR (red) in *Salmonella* spp. and certain serovars recovered from (a) broilers, (b) laying hens, and (c) fattening turkeys for all reporting countries, 2022

Resistance profiles exhibited by particular serovars

S. Typhimurium was the second and third most frequently reported serovar from cattle under 1 year of age (17.5%) and pigs (9.8%), respectively. Among *S. Typhimurium* isolates, MDR was reported at a very high level in pigs (56.9%) and at a high level in cattle under one year of age (35.7%; [Annex A.2](#), tables 4 and 8). The most common MDR profiles in pigs were CHL-AMP-SMX-TET (n = 16), CHL-AMP-SMX-TET (n = 9), CHL-AMP-NAL-CIP-SMX-TET (n = 9) and CHL-AMP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 9; Table). While two *S. Typhimurium* isolates from cattle under 1 year exhibited resistance to CHL-AMP-TGC-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET. *Salmonella* genomic island 1 (SGI1), known to contain a multidrug resistance region located on a complex class 1 integron designated In104, confers pentavalent resistance (i.e. ampicillin, chloramphenicol, streptomycin, sulfamethoxazole, tetracycline resistance phenotype – AMP-CHL-STR-SMX-TET) and has been widely documented in a range of *Salmonella* serovars.

Monophasic S. Typhimurium was the main serovar recovered from pigs (28.9%), the fourth in cattle under 1 year of age (n = 6), the seventh in laying hens (n = 22) and the eighth in turkeys (n = 25). Resistance to ampicillin, sulfamethoxazole, and tetracycline (AMP-SMX-TET) was the most frequent pattern in all food-producing animal populations, with 55.6% of MDR monophasic *S. Typhimurium* from pigs exhibiting it. The second leading pattern in pigs was resistance to CHL-AMP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 22). An addition of ciprofloxacin and nalidixic acid to the core resistance pattern (AMP-NAL-CIP-SMX-TET) was the second most observed pattern in turkeys and laying hens, and the third most in pigs.

Monophasic *S. Typhimurium* has spread widely among European pig populations. The AMP-SMX-TET resistance pattern (together with resistance to streptomycin) is typical of the European clone (ST34) of monophasic *S. Typhimurium* (Hopkins et al., 2010). The genes conferring resistance to these antimicrobials are commonly found in association together with IS26 mobile genetic elements, responsible for their integration at different chromosomal locations, as described in European strains of monophasic *S. Typhimurium* (Sun et al., 2020). It is noteworthy that multidrug resistance in the European clone of monophasic *S. Typhimurium* appears to have originated from the integration of MDR plasmids into the chromosome, facilitated by the presence of these IS26 mobile genetic elements (Sun et al., 2020).

S. Derby was the second and third most common serovar recovered from pigs (28.3%, N = 418) and turkeys (12.0%, N = 82), respectively. In pigs, the most common resistance pattern in MDR *S. Derby* was AMP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 15). MDR with quinolone resistance (ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid) was reported in isolates from all animal populations from which MDR *S. Derby* was recovered except cattle under 1 year of age. No *S. Derby* isolates exhibited combined resistance to quinolones and third-generation cephalosporins. Recent studies on *S. Derby* originating from the pork and poultry sectors in France identified four major host-specific lineages, corresponding to multilocus sequence typing (MLST) profiles ST39, ST40, ST71, and ST682 (Sévellec et al., 2018, 2020). The lineages ST39, ST40, and ST682 were associated with pork, and ST71 with poultry. While ST71 and ST682 isolates were generally devoid of resistance genes, ST40 isolates commonly harboured several resistance genes, with Clade 2 of this lineage characterised by SGI1 and the pattern of resistance to streptomycin, sulfonamides, and tetracycline. Additionally, a resistance gene for fosfomycin was detected in all genomes from ST39 (Sévellec et al., 2020). Moreover, *S. Derby* with ST40 from pigs, pork, wild boars and humans has also been reported in Spain with the most common phenotype conferred by the *tet(A)*, *aadA2* and *sul1* genes, located within identical or closely related variants of *Salmonella* Genomic Island 1 (SGI1; Vázquez et al., 2023). Two plasmid types (IncI1-Ia and pSC101-like), a class 1 integron, multiple insertion sequences and several intact or truncated transposons also shaped diverse resistance regions (Vazquez et al., 2023).

S. Rissen was the fourth most reported serovar from pigs in 2023 and exhibited high MDR levels (50.7%). The most frequent patterns found were CHL-AMP-TGC-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 9, all by Romania except one isolate reported by Portugal), GEN-CHL-AMP-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 8, all reported by Spain), and AMP-TGC-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 8, all reported by Portugal). Indeed, most MDR *S. Rissen* originated from Portugal, Romania and Spain. In 2015 – 2017 an increase in the number of human clinical cases caused by MDR *S. Rissen* (ST469) mainly in the Azores archipelago was observed with most Portuguese isolates showing a high degree of genetic relatedness and a potential link to pork production (Silveira et al., 2019). Also in Spain, a major MDR *S. Rissen* clone has been circulating in humans and animals (García-Fierro et al., 2016). Moreover, *tet(X4)* has been identified for the first time in *S. Rissen* (ST469) from pork in China (Zhang et al., 2024). The authors found that the *tet(X4)* was located in the IncFIA(HI1)-IncHI1A-IncHI1B(R27) hybrid plasmid, and the structure of *tet(X4)* was *abh-tet(X4)-ISCR2*, suggesting an increasing transmission risk of the mobile tigeicycline resistance gene *tet(X4)* beyond *E. coli* (Zhang et al., 2024).

S. Bredeney was the fourth most reported serovar in turkeys. Multidrug resistance was extremely high in this serovar among isolates recovered from turkeys (88.2%, n = 67). Notably, among these isolates, the level of MDR was greatly influenced by one MS, with Hungary reporting 64 multidrug-resistant isolates. Among MDR *S. Bredeney* isolates

recovered from turkeys, the most frequent pattern of resistance was to AMP-NAL-CIP-TET (n = 23, 34.3%), closely followed by the same pattern but with the addition of tigecycline and trimethoprim (AMP-TGC-NAL-CIP-TMP-TET; n = 22, 32.8%), and AMP-TGC-NAL-CIP-TET (n = 18, 26.9%), all reported by Hungary.

S. Infantis was the most frequently recovered serovar from broilers (40.0%) in 2022 and the second and third most reported in turkeys (13.0%) and in laying hens (8.5%), respectively ([Annex A.2](#), tables 11, 15 and 19).

Although a wide range of MDR patterns were reported among *S. Infantis* isolates from poultry, the most frequent MDR pattern was TGC-CIP-NAL-SMX-TET, detected in 29.8% of MDR isolates from broilers, 12.5% from laying hens, and 28.0% from turkeys. Resistance to five antimicrobial classes was noted among isolates from all poultry origins. Several *S. Infantis* isolates recovered from broilers showed MDR profiles AMP-CTX-CAZ-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 12), AMP-CTX-CAZ-TGC-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 19) and AMP-TGC-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET (n = 44). Four *S. Infantis* recovered from laying hens also exhibited a MDR pattern AMP-TGC-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET. While 14, 16 and eight *S. Infantis* isolates recovered from turkeys exhibited the following MDR patterns: AMP-CTX-CAZ-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET, AMP-CTX-CAZ-TGC-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET, and AMP-TGC-NAL-CIP-SMX-TMP-TET.